

Taking stock of built environment stock studies: Progress and prospects

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21 Abstract

22 Built environment stocks (buildings and infrastructures) play multiple roles in our socio-economic
23 metabolism: they serve as the backbone of modern societies and human well-being, drive the material
24 cycles throughout the economy, entail temporal and spatial lock-ins on energy use and emissions, and
25 represent an extensive reservoir of secondary materials. This review aims at providing a comprehensive
26 and critical review of the state of the art, progress, and prospects of built environment stocks research
27 which has boomed in the past decades. We include 249 publications published from 1985 to 2018,
28 conducted a bibliometric analysis, and assessed the studies by key characteristics including typology of
29 stocks (status of stock and end-use category), type of measurement (object and unit), spatial boundary
30 and level of resolution, and temporal scope. We also highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of
31 different estimation approaches. A comparability analysis of existing studies shows a clearly higher
32 level of stocks per capita and per area in developed countries and cities, confirming the role of
33 urbanization and industrialization in built environment stock growth. However, more spatially refined
34 case studies (e.g., on developing cities and non-residential buildings) and standardization and
35 improvement of methodology (e.g., with geographic information system and architectural knowledge)
36 and data (e.g., on material intensity and lifetime) would be urgently needed to reveal more robust
37 conclusions on the patterns, drivers, and implications of built environment stocks. Such advanced
38 knowledge on built environment stocks could foster societal and policy agendas such as urban
39 sustainability, circular economy, climate change, and United Nations 2030 Sustainable Development
40 Goals.

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48 1. Introduction

49 Society relies on the use of resources to fuel the multitude of socio-economic activities satisfying
50 human needs and well-being such as food, shelter, transportation, and communication. But today, as
51 the biophysical boundaries of our planet are increasingly transgressed,^{1,2} the environmental impacts
52 from primary resource production (e.g., energy use and greenhouse gas emissions) and waste disposal
53 have become burdensome.^{3,4} Materials accumulated in the anthroposphere in the form of buildings,
54 infrastructure, and consumer goods, however, constitute an extensive reservoir of secondary raw
55 materials as urban mines that should not be overlooked:⁵ more than half of all resources extracted
56 globally are used to expand and maintain anthropogenic material stocks and these stocks have
57 increased 23-fold in the past century.⁶ Considering further urbanization and industrialization worldwide
58 and the yet limited contribution of resource use reductions, re-use, and recycling in alleviating
59 pressures on the environment,^{7,8} substantial further growth of in-use stocks and consequent resource
60 use and environmental pressures are to be expected.⁹

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62 Already in 1941, Ostrolensk realized that “junked buildings, machinery, and automobiles” would, in
63 the near future, become an important source of raw materials.¹⁰ Two decades later, Jane Jacobs
64 regarded cities as “mines of the future”¹¹ and argued that “the largest, most prosperous cities will be the
65 richest, the most easily worked, and the most inexhaustible mines.”¹² But until the early 2000’s, socio-
66 economic metabolism research mostly focused on characterizing annual flows while the size and
67 dynamics of anthropogenic stocks remained the least understood parts of material cycles.^{13,14}

68
69 The recent decade have witnessed a fast-growing interest in the characterization of the patterns and
70 impacts of anthropogenic stocks, due largely to efforts of the industrial ecology and especially material
71 flow analysis (MFA) community. These studies cover a large variety of scopes, analyze numerous
72 aspects of stocks, and are conducted for very different purposes. For example, a number of studies
73 estimated the quantity and composition of materials accumulated in different reservoirs in different
74 parts of the world in order to identify potentials of secondary resources recovery.^{5,15–21} Economic
75 considerations on such recovery potentials have also been a focus.^{22,23} The temporal dynamics of stock
76 development have been analyzed^{24–28} to explore their historical patterns and socio-economic drivers.²⁹
77 The interaction between stocks and flows has been investigated in order to better understand the
78 influence (including possible lock-in effect³⁰) of stocks on material and energy demand^{1,29,31–34} and on

79 emissions.^{35–38} Life cycle assessment has been combined to material stock characterization to assess the
80 embodied energy³⁹ and end-of-life scenarios⁴⁰ of buildings and infrastructure stocks. The role of
81 anthropogenic stocks in human development, measured either by specific socio-economic indicators
82 (such as population and GDP)⁴¹ or composite indicators (such as Human Development Indicators³⁶)
83 have also been explored.

84

85 As anthropogenic stock research expands, gaps in knowledge, methodology, and data are also
86 becoming clear. To our knowledge, three relevant reviews in the past have identified gaps and
87 progresses of anthropogenic stock studies: in 2008, Gerst and Graedel¹⁴ synthesized the status and
88 implications of 54 studies on in-use stocks of metals; in 2014, Müller⁴² reviewed the methodologies
89 applied in 60 dynamic MFAs assessing past, present, and future stocks and flows of metals; in 2016,
90 Augiseau⁴³ reviewed 31 publications published between 1998 and 2015 focusing specifically on non-
91 metallic construction minerals. These reviews identified several patterns and gaps in anthropogenic
92 stock research, which we will build on in this review and elaborate further below.

- 93 • First, previous empirical studies have limited coverage geographically (e.g., few studies for less-
94 developed countries^{14,43}), material wise (e.g., lack of studies on some metals used in large quantities
95 such as zinc¹⁴), and end-use category wise (e.g., infrastructure stocks are less studied⁴³).
- 96 • Second, most existing studies focus on the quantification of anthropogenic stocks itself, but its
97 socioeconomic drivers (e.g., urban form), impacts (e.g., lock-in effects), and potentials to inform
98 relevant resource and environmental policy remain largely untapped yet.^{43,42} This is especially due
99 to lack of more spatially explicit results which could provide in-depth understanding for local
100 decision makers.¹⁴
- 101 • Third, methodologies in existing studies vary based on data availability^{42,43} and aim of study, but
102 they are often not consistent, making comparison and synthesis difficult, and uncertainty analysis
103 and full sensitivity analysis are often lacking as well.^{14,42}

104

105 However, these three reviews have a strong focus either on metals^{14,42} and non-metallic construction
106 materials⁴³ or dynamic modelling approach.⁴² Considering the booming research on anthropogenic
107 stock studies in the past decade and their varying scopes, purposes, and approaches, the aim of this
108 review is to provide an updated and comprehensive compilation of built environment stock studies. It

109 widens the scope to include all available literature, to our knowledge, on parts or totality of the built
110 environment stock, static or dynamic, from global to neighborhood level, and quantifying one or
111 several materials in terms of weight, dimensions, or number of items. This body of literature consists of
112 249 publications in English, German, French, Chinese, and Japanese, including grey literature such as
113 reports from different organizations (More information on the literature collection can be found in the
114 Supporting Information.) The earliest retrieved case-study dates back to 1985,⁴⁴ and the cut-off date of
115 literature search is 31 March 2018.

116

117 We provide an overview of the state of the art, progress, and prospects of built environment stocks
118 research through the analysis of bibliometrics (section 2), scope (section 3), estimation approaches
119 (section 4), and purposes (section 5) of all these studies published between 1985 and March 2018. We
120 have also included a comparability analysis of existing studies on construction material stocks at the
121 urban and national level (section 6), inferred the possible contributions of built environment stocks
122 results to informing a sustainable socio-metabolic transition and made recommendations for future
123 research (section 7).

124

125 **2. Definition and bibliometric analysis of built environment stock studies**

126 **2.1 Defining built environment stocks**

127 The anthropogenic material stocks consist of materials and products staying in the anthroposphere over
128 a certain period of time (usually more than one year in MFA). We categorized them into mobile stock
129 (e.g., consumer durables, machinery, and electronic equipment) and non-mobile stock (buildings and
130 infrastructure).⁴⁵ More precisely, the latter includes man-made buildings (residential and non-
131 residential) and infrastructure such as transportation infrastructure (road and rail network) and technical
132 infrastructure (e.g., for energy supply, telecommunication, water distribution and waste collection
133 networks) and is often called “built environment stocks”⁴⁵ (which is used consistently hereafter).

134

135 Figure 1a visualizes the anthropogenic stock in a “tree” structure: the different end-use categories of
136 the built environment stocks are represented in the form of branches upon which the mobile stocks,
137 represented by leaves, can be found. Human activities (e.g. to nourish, clean, transport, communicate,
138 reside, and work⁴⁶) and well-being, represented here as fruits, are structured in and supported by these

139 anthropogenic stocks. They are also sustained through continual inputs of materials, food, energy, and
 140 water and generate outputs of wastewater, construction and demolition waste, solid waste, and
 141 emissions.

142

143 The present review specifically covers the built environment stock and thus excludes studies focusing
 144 solely on mobile stocks. However, studies analyzing the aggregated anthropogenic stock, and thus
 145 including both mobile and built environment stocks, are within the scope. An example of such study is
 146 the quantification of copper stocks in Cape-Town,⁴⁷ which includes copper in buildings and
 147 infrastructures, but also in electrical and electronic products.

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149

150 **Figure 1** (a) Anthropogenic stocks as a tree. Branches represent the built environment stock end-use
 151 categories, and foliage represents the mobile stock categories. Information on the number of
 152 publications relative to each end-use can be found in SI. (b) The different dimensions of the scope of
 153 study in any stock analysis. The categories in grey are not considered in the present review.

154

155 2.2 Bibliometric analysis

156 The studied body of literature is composed of 249 studies, of which 178 are peer-reviewed journal
 157 articles. The remaining studies include conference proceedings (14), theses (13), and reports from
 158 different organizations (44) such as research project reports, white papers, and public or governmental
 159 reports. The number of studies has been increasing over the last two decades (Figure 2a), reflecting a
 160 growing interest in the understanding of built environment stocks. More than half of the peer-reviewed
 161 journal articles were published in four journals (Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Journal of

162 Industrial Ecology, Building Research & Information, and Environmental Science & Technology)
163 (Figure 2a).

164

165 Additionally, an evaluative bibliometric analysis was conducted on peer-reviewed journal articles
166 published in English. The two most prolific authors in the field, Daniel B. Müller and Hiroki Tanikawa
167 (Figure 2b), are also at the center of two clusters of built environment stock researchers (Figure 2c)
168 based in Europe (mainly Norway, Denmark, Netherlands, Austria, and Germany) and East Asia
169 (mainly Japan and China). In Europe, Müller's dynamic MFA model for quantifying future material
170 stocks²⁹ has been further developed and used by his colleagues in a number of studies, mostly at a
171 national level. In Japan, Tanikawa developed a methodology integrating Geographical Information
172 System (GIS) into bottom-up studies⁴⁸ for quantifying and locating construction material stocks over
173 time (4d-GIS) at an urban and national level, which has since been widely used in case studies
174 elsewhere.

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178 **Figure 2.** Bibliometrics over the body of built environment stocks literature (Figure (a) includes all 249
 179 publications, and Figures (b)-(d) include peer-reviewed journal articles in English only). (a) Number of
 180 publications per year and number of articles published in different peer-reviewed journals or grey
 181 literature. Note that the year 2018 only includes publications up to March 2018, and a factor 4 was
 182 applied to approximate a result over the whole year. Abbreviations – RCR: Resource, Conservation &
 183 Recycling; JIE: Journal of Industrial Ecology; BRI: Building Research & Information; EST:
 184 Environmental Science & Technology; (b) Tag cloud of the journal article authors, with the size of
 185 names proportional to number of journal articles that author published (both first author and
 186 contributing author roles are counted; see details in Table S2 in Supporting Information); (c) Network
 187 of co-authorship; and (d) Co-citation network of key literature on built environment stocks. The top
 188 twenty cited articles can be found in Supporting Information.

189

190 **3. Characteristics of built environment stock studies**

191 The scope of a stock study is defined through three dimensions (Figure 1b), namely “typology and
192 measurement”, “spatial boundary and level of resolution”, and “temporal scope”. Figure 3 shows the
193 results of the scope analysis for the reviewed body of literature.

194

195 **3.1 Typology and measurement**

196 The typology and measurement dimension can be categorized into “status of stock”, “end-use
197 category”, “object of measurement”, and “unit of measurement”.

198

199 *3.1.1 Status of stock*

200 The status of stock, derived from Kapur and Graedel’s work, includes employed stock (extracted from
201 nature for human use, not yet discarded) and expended stock (discarded after use or dissipated).⁴⁹ The
202 present review focuses on employed stock, composed of “in-use stock” (being used by humans, e.g.,
203 vehicles on the road) and “hibernating stock” (not actively used anymore but not yet discarded, e.g.,
204 obsolete underground water pipes).⁴⁹ The majority of studies include in-use stock, except a few studies
205 focusing solely on hibernating stock.^{18,50} However, inconsistencies in typology of stocks in the body of
206 literature hinder a deeper analysis of the status of stocks under investigation. An example of such
207 definition mismatch is the one on dissipated stock. While Kapur and Graedel⁴⁹ define it as the amount
208 of resources that went back to nature and is impossible to recover, Tanikawa and Hashimoto⁴⁸
209 exemplify it as material stocked underground and remaining there after the above structure was
210 removed, thus equivalent to Kapur and Graedel’s “hibernating stock” definition. Kapur and Graedel’s⁴⁹
211 in-use stock is coined as “social stock” by Yue et al.⁵¹ Daigo et al⁵² name the combination of obsolete
212 stock and in-use stock “overall stock”, while Kapur and Graedel coin it “employed stock”. Krook et
213 al⁵³ classify metal stocks into “active” (including in-use stocks) and “inactive” (subdivided into
214 “controlled”, thus including hibernating stocks, and “uncontrolled”). In general, it seems that in-use
215 stock studies often include hibernating stocks as part of the in-use stocks, unless stated specifically.

216

217 *3.1.2 End-use*

218 The end-use category refers to different functional uses of buildings (e.g., residential, office, and
219 commercial) and infrastructure (e.g., roads, power plant, and pipes). A detailed categorization of end-
220 use categories was developed (Figure 1a) to consistently classify each case study and allow for

221 identification of patterns in the body of literature. (See Figure S1 in Supporting Information for
222 detailed frequency count on end-use in the body of literature).

223

224 Almost half of the studies (48%) consider the totality of the anthropogenic stock, which can be
225 explained by the large amount of studies quantifying the amount of a specific material (often a metal)
226 stocked in the anthroposphere, through a top-down approach that uses statistical data for material
227 consumption in major product categories and their lifetime (see details in section 4). Of the remaining
228 studies, about half look at the building stock while only a few focus on infrastructures, reflecting a
229 higher interest in buildings which may cause an oversight of the importance of infrastructures in stock
230 dynamics.

231

232 One striking feature is that definitions of different end-use categories vary a lot. For example, a
233 residential building stock may be referred to as a domestic building,⁵⁴ or dwelling stock.⁵⁵ Non-
234 residential buildings can be studied as an end-use of its own,³ or can be defined as “non-domestic
235 building” by opposition to domestic buildings.⁵⁴ Some studies refer to commercial buildings⁵⁶ or
236 industrial buildings,⁴⁷ and some also refer to non-residential buildings as part of the overall dwelling
237 stock.⁴⁷ Classifying building uses is a complicated task, and many countries have their own
238 classification. Such inconsistencies in definitions hinder comparisons between studies, thus making it
239 difficult to identify patterns in a transparent way.

240

241 *3.1.3 Object of measurement*

242 The object of measurement includes substance (e.g., copper¹⁸), material (e.g., cement⁵⁷), component
243 (e.g., window frame⁵⁸), product (e.g., floor⁵⁹), or the entire building. It should be noted that in cases
244 measuring stocks in dimensions or number of units, such as a study of the number of buildings in a
245 city’s building stock, the object of measurement (building) is the same as the end-use category.

246

247 Almost half of the literature on stocks focuses on one or several metals. A large share focuses on
248 several construction materials, including metals and bulk construction materials. The list of
249 construction materials under consideration is different for each study, making results difficult to
250 compare. The most studied materials are steel, copper, timber, concrete, and aluminum (Figure 3b).

251 The rest of the studies measure stock in terms of number of items or dimensions and typically do not
 252 focus on any specific material.

253

254 *3.1.4 Unit of measurement.*

255 A stock can be quantified through different units: number of items (e.g., number of buildings⁶⁰);
 256 dimensional units such as the total length of pipe in a city⁶¹ (m), the floor area of a residential building
 257 stock⁵⁹ (m²), or the total volume of material (e.g., m³ of clay in single detached housing stocks²¹); or
 258 weight of material (e.g., tons of steel⁵²). The stock results are also sometimes displayed through
 259 indicators measured as stock values relative to land area (e.g., mass of material per square meters) or
 260 population (e.g., mass per capita and floor area per capita) for comparability.

261

262 Most studies (88%) characterize stocks in mass-related units (Figure 3a), including indicators derived
 263 from absolute results (e.g., mass/capita or mass/sq.km) which allow for comparison of stocks in
 264 different places or times. As specified earlier, a small share of the literature quantifies stocks in terms
 265 of physical dimensions such as volume^{16,21,62} or floor area of building stocks,^{32,59,63} or length of roads,⁶⁴
 266 while the remaining studies accounts for the number of specific items (e.g., buildings^{25,65-67} or
 267 windows⁵⁸).

268

269 **3.2 Spatial boundary and level of resolution**

270 Stock studies are conducted at different geographical scales, ranging from neighborhood, urban,
 271 regional, national, multinational (several countries) to global scale. While some studies quantify the
 272 total stock within the given geographical boundary, others include a higher spatial resolution (e.g., a
 273 global stock study could have resolution for each nation and an urban stock study could have data per
 274 square kilometers).

275

276 The spatial boundaries over the body of literature span from global (17) to building-level (3), while the
 277 spatial resolution varies from virtually no resolution⁶⁸⁻⁷¹ to spatially very refined results.⁷²

- 278 • A few studies at the global scale have results refined to the level of groups of countries⁶ or to
 279 national levels.^{27,69}
- 280 • 55% of the studies were conducted on a national level (Figure 3d). Each country in the world
 281 has been studied at least once, as part of an effort to characterize the stock of a single material

282 such as aluminum²⁷ or steel⁷³ of all world's countries. China and Japan were studied the most,
 283 with respectively 43 and 29 studies related to (parts of) their built environment stock (Figure
 284 3e). Most studies at the national level resulted in stock characterization at the nation level. A
 285 handful are however refined to a regional level⁷⁴⁻⁷⁹ or further.

- 286 • Seventeen articles report results for stocks on regional levels (part of a country). It is worth
 287 noting that due to differences in country size, a regional study in a country can be
 288 geographically wider than a national study for another country.
- 289 • On an urban scale, 86 cities were studied in 58 publications. For example, studies for the city of
 290 Beijing in China calculated the amount of construction material stocked in its entire built
 291 environment stock,⁸⁰ residential building system,⁸¹ and road system,⁸² and the amount of
 292 concrete stocked in its residential buildings.⁸³ Vienna is another city that has been studied from
 293 different angles: construction material stocked in its buildings over time⁸⁴ and in its subway
 294 network⁸⁵, and the total amount of copper⁸⁶ and lead⁸⁷ stock in the city. One single study
 295 estimated the material stocked in infrastructure in 40 US cities based on road scaling patterns
 296 and distance from the city center⁶⁴, explaining the numerous urban studies “dotted” in the U.S.
 297 on the map. Studies at the urban level can be refined to a neighborhood,^{47,87,88} hectare⁴⁰ or up to
 298 square meters resolution.^{64,89,90} In other cases, results are presented at the study object level.
 299 This is the case for studies on transportation networks, where the geographical resolution is
 300 visualized through maps depicting the location of the network under study, e.g., different
 301 subway lines⁸⁵ or different road types over a city.⁸²
- 302 • Four articles also report stock results at a neighborhood scale, i.e., the PolyVinyl Chloride stock
 303 in buildings in an Amsterdam neighborhood,⁹¹ the dynamics of the material stock of buildings,
 304 roadways, and railways in Salford Quays in Manchester, UK and Wakayama City Center in
 305 Japan.⁴⁸

306

307 **3.2 Temporal scope**

308 41% of the reviewed studies characterize stocks in a static way, giving a snapshot of the state of the
 309 stock at a specific year. The rest of studies are dynamic, as they consider the evolution of stock over
 310 time. Studies focusing on the historical dynamics of stock are “retrospective”, while studies analyzing
 311 future development of stock are “prospective”. The temporal scope of dynamic studies varies greatly,
 312 from a few years to over a century (Figure 3c). Studies taking into account long historical

313 periods^{48,73,92-95} are good basis for analyzing dynamics of stocks over time and providing insights into
 314 the non-linear waste and recycling potentials due to stock dynamics. By coupling changes in stock to
 315 events such as natural disasters^{96,97} or wars,^{25,93} links to broader socio-economic issues can be made.
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317
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 319 **Figure 3** Scope of the built environment stocks literature. (a) Object and unit of measurement over the
 320 body of literature. (b) Main materials studied over the body of literature. *A number of studies present
 321 results aggregated in material groups such as “construction materials” or “metals”. (c) Time scopes of
 322 studies categorized by methodologies (top-down, bottom-up and other approaches are defined and
 323 discussed in details in section 4). The blue-orange bar charts depict the time scales of retrospective
 324 and/or prospective dynamic studies. Note that two publications include two case studies at once,
 325 resulting in a total of 251 case-studies over 249 publications. (d) Spatial boundary and spatial
 326 resolution of studies. Almost half of the case studies were performed at the national scale, with no
 327 further spatial differentiation. “Object-scale” refers to studies spatially refined to the levels of e.g.,

328 buildings, or entire subway network. (e) Geographical distribution of case studies on the national and
329 urban levels.

330

331 **4. Overview, development, and critical discussion of the different estimation** 332 **approaches**

333 The body of literature was screened in terms of estimating approaches which are generally categorized
334 into top-down approach, bottom-up approach, and their combination and extension.^{14,42,72,73,98} Figure 3c
335 shows that the numbers of studies using the top-down approach (102) and the bottom-up approach
336 (115) were almost equal. A few other methods were also used in the literature, especially a remote
337 sensing based approach (10) and hybrid approaches (7) that use bottom-up results to calibrate top-down
338 models. These different estimating methods each have strengths and weaknesses, and should be chosen
339 in accordance with the purpose of the study and data availability.

340

341 **4.1 Top-down approach**

342 The top-down approach builds on the mass-balance principle that the change in stock is the result of the
343 difference between inflows and outflows of a material over time, usually over a year.⁴² Over the body
344 of literature, the term “top-down” is used inconsistently, leading authors to sometimes name their
345 methodology in a more descriptive manner (e.g. residence time model⁹⁹ or population balance
346 model⁵²). In top-down studies, historical development of employed stocks (retrospective study) is thus
347 actually calculated through a flow-driven approach.¹⁰⁰ Data on inflows of material are usually available
348 (e.g., from statistical agencies, industry associations, non-governmental organizations, and scientific
349 literature) over long period of time. But outflow data are much more difficult to track, and are thus
350 often calculated through estimated lifetime of product and infrastructure.

351

352 The approach is particularly efficient in achieving an overview of the stock dynamics over long periods
353 of time (Figure 3c). For example, based on a top-down approach, per capita in-use iron stocks in a few
354 industrialized countries are found to saturate since the 1970s,¹⁰¹ and a few advanced economies (e.g.,
355 Japan, Italy, Germany) show trends of steady speed or deceleration in their material stock
356 accumulation.²⁴ However, globally and for major world-regions, no saturation of total in-use material
357 stocks can be found.⁶

358

359 These identified historical patterns of built environment stocks in industrialized countries may be used
360 as a benchmark for future development pathways (e.g., potential saturation levels of stocks) of
361 developing countries. Such an approach to use identified stock patterns as driver for simulating future
362 material cycles and demand, introduced by Müller in 2006²⁹ in a study of the Dutch dwelling stock
363 from 1900 to 2100, has been further used and developed in many other studies over the past
364 years.^{45,59,63,83,96,102} The underlying logic of this method is that in-use stocks reflect directly the service
365 levels (e.g., m² of shelter and ton- or person-km of mobility), behave more robustly than flows in the
366 long term as they are not affected by short-term oscillations in consumption,⁷⁴ and set boundary
367 conditions for raw material demand and potentials for recycling at the end-of-life of products and
368 infrastructure.⁹⁶

369

370 However, since historical shipment or apparent consumption data are mainly available on the global
371 and national levels and for broad categories only through industry statistics, the spatial resolution of
372 top-down studies rarely surpasses the national level and they usually do not have a resolution on the
373 individual product or infrastructure level (aggregated product categories instead). This hinders a
374 detailed understanding of the location and quality of anthropogenic stocks. In addition, average lifetime
375 is a key parameter for modeling stock accumulation in the top-down approach (lifetime distribution
376 functions almost does not affect the stock modeling, but is a key factor in accurately projecting future
377 flows of demolition waste),¹⁰³ but there are very few empirical data and thus huge uncertainty on
378 lifetime (particularly difficult to assume a reasonable average lifetime for product categories that
379 include many heterogeneous products¹⁰⁴). For example, Huang et al estimated the Chinese building
380 stock through a top-down approach as 84 tons/cap in 2010.¹⁰⁵ A bottom-up approach of only the
381 residential buildings in China yielded a result four times inferior (24 tons/cap) for 2008.⁷⁵ Although the
382 bottom-up study investigated a smaller part of the built environment than the top-down study, this
383 difference in results is still noteworthy and might also be explained by methodological differences. For
384 example, lifetime of buildings is a critical factor of top-down estimations that is very poorly understood
385 in China.¹⁰⁶

386

387 **4.2 Bottom-up approach**

388 The bottom-up approach (also called coefficient based approach⁵) quantifies the amount of stock “piece
389 by piece”, by counting all items containing a specific material and multiplying the number of each

390 specific product by its material intensity. Bottom-up approach for stock estimation is therefore highly
391 data and labor intensive.

392

393 Because they are directly derived from information on stock inventory, results of bottom-up studies are
394 usually deemed to be more accurate than those obtained through a top-down approach. Moreover, the
395 bottom-up approach is advantageous in regards to spatial and content differentiation of results. Bottom-
396 up studies thus contribute to an improved comprehension of the physical arrangement of the system¹⁰⁷
397 and provide a detailed understanding of the composition of the stock,⁷² especially for studies focusing
398 on a defined areas.¹⁰⁷

399

400 However, because of the large amount of data required to conduct such study, the scope of bottom-up
401 studies is often narrowed down to a smaller geographical scale (national level or below), specific year
402 (snapshots),²⁸ specific materials, and usually to those types of stocks, where such information is
403 actually available (which partially explains why so many studies on residential buildings exist). Indeed,
404 if the bottom-up approach is applied to a wide scope, limitations and uncertainties arise concerning
405 data for inventories of products, material applications, and material intensity data.¹⁰⁷ In order to
406 overcome these limitations (on material intensity and stock inventory), researchers have identified a
407 few complementing ways.

408 • **The use of building archetypes.** The use of “building archetype” consists of classifying the
409 building stock according to types (or building use), cohorts (or age of construction), and/or the
410 combination of the two into theoretical buildings called “archetypes”.¹⁰⁸ By weighting each
411 archetype by the number of buildings fitting the archetype description, the heterogeneous data sets
412 of building stocks are homogenized, thus facilitating analysis.¹⁰⁹ Though the approach has
413 primarily been used for modelling energy performance of building stocks,^{110–113} building
414 archetypes have also been used for material stock studies, by applying an average material intensity
415 coefficient to each archetype stock. For example, Ortlepp used building archetypes on a national
416 scale in Germany, by homogenizing the heterogeneous stock that are non-residential buildings.¹¹⁴
417 Ergun used the approach on the urban scale and inventoried the amount of clay bricked stocked in
418 Toronto’s single detached house to examine the availability of the material for urban mining
419 purposes.²¹ In the Netherlands, researchers developed building stock models by linking building
420 archetypes with cadastral information, for the purpose of city planning and the circular

421 transition.¹¹⁵⁻¹²² It is worthy to note that, the archetype approach unavoidably generates
422 uncertainties at different levels.¹²³ For example, Ortlepp et al raised the representativeness issue of
423 building materials content data based on sample buildings (due to lack of official statistics). By
424 comparing a simplified archetype classification (based only on building type) to a building-age
425 concept (archetypes based on both building type and age cohort), they also found that an increased
426 level of differentiation could better model reality, allow for more precise estimation of
427 uncertainties, and increase the range of applicability of results, but meanwhile raise the data
428 collection challenge and level of uncertainty.

429 • **Integrating Geographical Information System (GIS) tools and data in bottom-up studies.** GIS,
430 as a tool for handling, processing and analyzing large amount of geospatial data, allows for higher
431 spatial resolution and improved understanding of the physical system and composition of built
432 environment stock. In order to conduct a GIS-based bottom-up analysis, two crucial types of data
433 are required.¹²⁴ First, spatial data that contains information on the geo-localization of buildings and
434 infrastructures, as well as attributes such as type of buildings and infrastructure or year of
435 construction. Second, material stock intensity data that informs on the material composition of
436 buildings and infrastructures and that, ideally, should be specific to each and every building and
437 infrastructure. But as of today, most GIS databases do not include such “bill of material”
438 information, and studies rely on average material intensity coefficients derived from building
439 archetypes. Still, the few existing GIS-based bottom-up studies have proved to yield more detailed
440 results than other methodologies. Tanikawa, a pioneer in the integration of GIS in bottom-up
441 studies, analyzed the Japanese built environment stock through a GIS-based bottom-up study⁴⁸ that
442 resulted in an estimation of 170 tons/cap in 2010. In contrast, top-down studies of Japan resulted in
443 higher estimations ranging from 236 tons/cap of construction minerals in 2000¹²⁵ to 310 tons/cap of
444 construction materials in 2005.²⁸ On an urban level, Beijing’s 2013 road stock was studied in a
445 bottom-up fashion in two different studies. While the study without use of GIS yielded c.a. 1
446 ton/cap of construction material,⁸⁰ the GIS-based study yielded results 7-fold higher.⁸² Although the
447 difference can be partly explained by the inclusion of e.g., ancillary facilities (20% of the results),
448 such difference reflect also the usefulness of GIS for a detailed assessment of built environment
449 stocks.

450 • **Refining archetypes with GIS data.** The use of average material intensity for building archetypes
451 also generates uncertainties as they fail to capture detailed information on the geometry and

452 construction assemblies of each building. For example, Stephan et al estimates a possible error of
453 20% in calculating the amount of material stocked in outer walls, depending on the geometry of the
454 buildings.³⁹ Since this uncertainty was calculated based on outer wall geometry only, the potential
455 variation in material stocks of the whole buildings, neighborhoods, or cities could be even higher.
456 To address such geometrical issues, the authors drew on GIS data of Melbourne's buildings
457 footprints. They studied the city's building stock through a disaggregated approach integrating
458 building geometry and architectural knowledge of experts in order to derive bill of material and
459 assemblies quantities for each building. Developing systematic reporting of bill of materials for
460 each building within a country would be commendable in order to facilitate detailed studies of built
461 environment material stock composition. Some on-going initiatives include for example "Building
462 Passports" or "Materials Passports" tools and database (sets of data describing defined
463 characteristics of materials in products that give them value for recovery and reuse), e.g., in the EU
464 project "Buildings As Material Banks"¹²⁶ and Dutch Madaster platform.

465 • **Integrating the time dimension in bottom-up studies.** The majority of bottom-up studies in the
466 literature have been conducted in a static manner. Thirty-five studies, though, yielded dynamic
467 results in an effort to depict and analyze the changes of stock over time. Dynamic bottom-up
468 studies are in fact dense series of static results. Increments vary from one^{72,80} to ten years⁸⁸ in the
469 literature. For example, in 2009, Meinel et al studied the spatial and temporal development of
470 building stock of a German city over 20 years.⁹⁰ Topographic map data and information on the
471 buildings physical structures were added into a GIS model, which showed the changes of material
472 stock over time in the city.⁹⁰ The same year, Tanikawa and Hashimoto⁴⁸ studied the development of
473 material stock in two urban neighborhood, one in Japan and one in the UK. They developed a 4d-
474 GIS framework in which the time dimension is integrated into the GIS tool to geo-reference the
475 changes in material stock distribution over time, which has since been used for a few other studies
476 (e.g., Ezhou city in China from 1970 to 2013¹²⁷ or the whole Japan at a spatial resolution of 1
477 sq.km over 65 years⁷²). Integrating the time dimension to GIS studies allows to answer both
478 questions of "when" and "where" did material accumulate, which enables a spatial-temporal
479 analysis of patterns and impacts of stock accumulation regarding, for example, the role of urban
480 forms in urban stock accumulation and urban mining potentials.⁴⁸

481

482 4.3 Remote sensing

483 The use of remote sensing technologies has been on the rise in the recent years in material stock
484 research, inspired by the findings that the radiance of nighttime lights (NTL) correlate well with human
485 activity and socioeconomic parameters^{128–130} such as population, energy consumption, gross domestic
486 product (GDP), and CO₂ emissions.^{130,131} Rauch¹³² used the linear relationship between GDP and a
487 handful of available stock data to estimate the global in-use stock of four metals (Al, Cu, Fe, and Zn) in
488 2000 and produced a 1km-by-1km resolution map. Takahashi et al.^{133,134} confirmed the feasibility of
489 this approach by studying the relationship between NTL and in-use copper stock (the correlation
490 originated from the copper in electric wiring), and concluded that the “NTL/in-use stock method”
491 yields more accurate results than “GDP/in-use stock method”. Additionally, studies showed that
492 building steel stock is highly correlated to urban NTL, while infrastructure steel stock is correlated to
493 total NTL,⁷⁹ and that certain types of NTL images have greater modeling capability than others for in-
494 use steel stock studies.¹³⁵

495

496 This method is beneficial as NTL images are readily available for the entire world, over many years,
497 and countries lacking statistical data can still be analyzed in a relatively low cost, high spatial
498 resolution (generally 1 km^{79,132,134} and up to 500m¹³⁵), and highly efficient manner.¹³⁵ Therefore, the
499 results can be used to identify stock-intensive areas that would deserve further refined study. However,
500 these generated data at a high-resolution level should be interpreted with care due to inherent limitation
501 of this method, such the full nighttime light saturation effect¹³² and scale effect. Furthermore, these
502 results do not robustly describe the physical system (e.g., no information for underground built
503 environment stocks), nor the material composition, age and quality of the stocks studied. They
504 generally present static results only as well because the NTL imagery are literally picture of light-
505 emitting structures at one point in time (Similarly to bottom-up studies, the time dimension can be
506 introduced through the compilation of results over a series of years¹³⁴).

507

508 4.4 Other approaches

509 Chen and Graedel¹⁰⁴ classified stock estimation approaches using product level data over long time
510 spans as four quadrants: flow-based vs stock-based and using physical data vs. using monetary data.
511 They found the use of monetary data (both flow-based and stock-based approaches), coupled to
512 “material content per monetary unit” coefficients, could allow the physical quantification of related in-

513 use stocks. Such monetary data have the advantage of becoming increasingly available in the form of
514 annual investment flows and Input-Output (I/O) tables, particularly in the US and Japan, over long
515 timespans. They successfully apply the methodologies to the case of aluminum use in automobiles in
516 the US. Although not specifically applied to built environment stocks, the “Flow-Based using
517 Monetary Data” method is deemed usable for calculating in-use stock of materials that have detailed
518 I/O tables in relevant sectors. In the US for example, aluminum, copper, iron, and plastics have
519 products or products groups in the sectors of building and structures and transportation facilities.

520
521 Bottom-up and top-down approaches have been used complementarily in order to reduce uncertainties
522 by using elements from a methodology to support the other approach in cases where data are lacking.⁹⁸
523 Schiller et al increased the robustness of their conclusions by quantifying the uncertainty in their study
524 of Germany’s anthropogenic stock and by contrasting complete but less detailed top-down results with
525 incomplete but partially more robust bottom-up results.⁵ In very few studies, bottom-up results were
526 integrated in top-down studies as a mean of calibrating the model.^{136–138}

527
528 Tanikawa⁷² and Fishman¹³⁹ argued that such calibrated top-down studies could in turn be used to
529 calibrate remote sensing approaches, and could also help develop more accurate scenarios based on an
530 improved understanding of the relation between material stock and socio-economic indicators. In
531 conclusion, the different approaches to characterize material stocks are thus not self-excluding, and
532 comparing and hybridizing approaches would be a fruitful way to increase robustness of results⁷² and
533 overcome limitations inherent to each approach.

534

535 **5. Purposes and implications of studies**

536 In addition to theoretical and methodological development mentioned above, existing built
537 environment stock studies often go beyond and aim to inform relevant stakeholders in their waste
538 management, urban mining, spatial planning, circular economy, and resource efficiency strategies.

539

540 Retrospective dynamic studies are useful to identify trends and patterns (e.g., potential levels of
541 saturation¹⁰¹) as well as potential drivers such as economical growth^{33,140,141} or population growth¹⁴² in
542 historical stock development. The age distribution of stocks and connected operational energy use and
543 future waste flows can also be investigated, as well as potentials for recycling^{143–146} (extent to which

544 recycling has occurred^{168,93,147,148} or material turnover⁹²). Such information can assist authorities and
545 governmental decision-makers, and ultimately different industry stakeholders, in developing
546 appropriate life cycle management measures.⁵⁷

547

548 In prospective dynamic studies, scenarios are developed to forecast the evolution of stocks and related
549 flows under different conditions. Drivers identified in retrospective studies can be used to develop
550 these scenarios and model possible future developments of material cycles, such as their
551 demand,^{27,29,69,105,125,149,150} production and consumption,^{151,152} waste generation,^{29,105,153} availability as
552 secondary resources,^{16,99,153} associated energy use^{27,151} and CO2 emissions.^{27,35,105,151,154} Developing
553 scenario also allows to study the impact of introducing policies and strategies such as material
554 efficiency,¹⁵⁵ energy reduction,^{32,108} technological substitution,¹⁵⁶ prolonging lifetime of buildings and
555 infrastructures,¹⁵⁷ or improving material recovery rate.²⁰ Scenario development can also be used to
556 assess what strategies are needed and what are their contributions to reach a specific target, e.g., a
557 global saturation of per capita stocks,⁶⁹ developing countries reaching infrastructure levels of industrial
558 countries,³⁵ emission cuts,³⁷ and addressing housing deficiency in developing countries.⁶⁶

559

560 Stock studies are also conducted to characterize stocks in a high level of detail to gain knowledge on
561 material quantity in different products or end-uses (mostly at the urban or regional scale), which yield
562 results valuable to different stakeholders. For example, potentials for city-level material reuse and
563 recycling^{19,21,158} can assist decision makers for sustainable planning, while new or improved knowledge
564 on recycling, mining and mineral processing sectors¹⁵⁹ can assist waste management companies in
565 targeting relevant waste categories for recycling.¹⁶⁰

566

567 A number of case studies include additionally the spatial distribution of different material stocks across
568 a city or a region to identify urban mining opportunities^{5,39,161} such as materials stocked in hibernating
569 infrastructure stocks.¹⁸ Spatial information is also used for assisting development of location-specific
570 strategies for the reduction of environmental impacts of buildings and settlements.¹⁶² Construction and
571 demolition waste management^{15,40,163} can be planned in more details by assessing the technology
572 required to recover future available secondary material or product,¹⁵⁹ as well as planning of
573 transportation routes and location of facilities for storage of recovered secondary resources.

574

575 However, developing recycling and urban mining strategies requires additional information on
576 technical and socioeconomic drivers and constraints, but such feasibility analysis is still largely
577 missing. Worth noting is the work of Van Beers et al which analyzed copper and zinc recycling
578 potential in Australia and developed a priority assessment matrix to evaluate all copper and zinc's end-
579 of-life flows from in-use stock according to quantity, material properties, and location (most
580 economical in the dense urban centers).¹⁶⁴ Krook and colleagues analyzed the economic conditions to
581 mine copper from hibernating power cables in Swedish cities,^{23,165} and concluded that, unless
582 infrastructure managers integrate the resource recovery process into their system upgrades project, the
583 extraction of copper does not make economic sense.

584

585 **6. Drivers and comparability of built environment stock results**

586 We have collected empirical results of all studies whose scope focus on the weight of the totality of
587 construction materials, in one or several parts of the built environment stock, at the national or urban
588 scales, to allow for comparability or consistency check on a per-capita and per-km² level. At the urban
589 scale, 22 publications satisfied such scope, covering 26 cities or urban areas; at the national scale, 19
590 countries are covered over 18 publications. Figure 4 visualizes the results on per capita and per km²
591 levels. Although the heterogeneity of the scopes of the studies (different spatial scale, end-use, type of
592 stock, materials, years, and methodologies) hinder accurate comparison, a number of key conclusions
593 can be drawn.

594

595

596 **Figure 4.** Results of studies quantifying construction material stocks in terms of mass at the urban and
 597 national scales. (a) Material Stock per capita (t/cap). (b) Material Stock per km² (kt/km²). Note the
 598 scale difference between urban and national results. Abbreviations of estimation approaches – BU:
 599 Bottom-Up, gBU: GIS-based Bottom-Up, TD: Top-Down; Abbreviations of countries – AT: Austria,
 600 AU: Australia, BE: Belgium, BR: Brazil, CH: Switzerland, CN: China, DE: Germany, FR: France, GB:
 601 United-Kingdom, ID: Indonesia, JP: Japan, LU: Luxembourg, NO: Norway, PE: Peru, TW: Taiwan,
 602 US: USA. *2.6 km² in Philadelphia (University City); 11 km² in Manchester (Salford); 8 km² in

603 Wakayama (City Center). Urban studies: Oslo (NO)¹⁶⁶, Salford Quays Manchester (GB)⁴⁸, Vienna
 604 (AT)^{84,85,167}, Frankfurt (DE)³, Esch-sur-Alzette (LU)⁴⁰, Geneva (CH)¹⁶⁸, Bruxelles (BE)¹⁶⁹, Orléans
 605 (FR)¹⁷⁰, Paris (FR)¹⁷¹, Kitakyushu (JP)¹⁷², Wakayama (JP)⁴⁸, Taipei City (TW)¹⁷, Melbourne (AU)³⁹,
 606 Jakarta (ID)¹⁷³, Bandung (ID)¹⁷³, Beijing (CN)⁸⁰⁻⁸², Tianjing (CN)⁸⁰, Shanghai (CN)⁸⁰, Ezhou City
 607 (CN)¹²⁷, Philadelphia (US)¹⁷⁴, Rio de Janeiro (BR)¹⁶³, and Chiclayo (PE)¹⁵. National studies:
 608 Austria¹⁷⁵, Germany^{5,77,114}, Switzerland^{162,176}, Japan^{28,72,78,94,125,153}, China^{75,105,177-179}, and USA^{28,142}.

609

610 Urban areas accumulate the largest share of anthropogenic stock. Indeed, as center of population,
 611 production and consumption, they are characterized by a higher density of buildings and infrastructures
 612 than their hinterlands. While national built material stock accounts range from about 20 (Austria) to
 613 100+ (Japan) kt/km², urban accounts rise to about 1000-1200 kt/km² in Vienna (Austria) and about
 614 1000 kt/km² in Wakayama City (Japan). The smallest area studied in the literature, 2.6 km² of
 615 Philadelphia, US, accounts for about 1400 kt/km² of construction material stock, against 10 kt/km² for
 616 the US national average. Studies focusing on urban areas are thus very appropriate to better
 617 characterize and understand materials stocks, be it for urban mining purposes or overall understanding
 618 of stock dynamics and drivers.

619

620 Per capita levels of developed countries are overall higher than developing countries, both at a national
 621 and urban level. Overall construction material stocks in Chinese and Indonesian cities, as of 2012-
 622 2013, are less than 50 t/cap in residential or total building stocks while European cities levels are up to
 623 4 times higher, with Vienna amounting to about 200-300 t/cap. Material stocks in Wakayama (Japan)
 624 and Melbourne's (Australia) reach about the same level as Vienna's, indicating a potential common
 625 pattern in mature cities. The differences between developing cities and mature cities could empirically
 626 be explained by differences in socio-economic development. Fishman et al showed that material stock
 627 accumulation in Japan prefectures was linked to driving factors such as economic and population
 628 growth, as well as population density.⁴¹ In countries like Japan, high levels of material stocks in the
 629 built environment are also explained by the demanding infrastructure and building codes necessary to
 630 prevent damages from earthquake and typhoons.⁴⁸ But it is presently challenging to analyze in details
 631 the reasons and drivers of such differences due to different focus of each study. More empirical studies
 632 on other typical cities across the world would thus be profitable to obtain better understanding of their
 633 drivers and implications.

634

635 Non-residential buildings account for an important share of the building stocks. Bottom-up studies
636 quantified their share from about a quarter¹⁷⁵ to almost half^{5,114} of the total building stock. Still, non-
637 residential buildings are less studied than residential buildings because their diversified functions and
638 components lead to a lack of data thus hindering their analysis.¹¹⁴ But such buildings are believed to
639 contain a high share of valuable secondary resources such as metals³ due to these very characteristics.
640 Moreover, a share of non-residential buildings (e.g., commercial or industrial buildings) is dependent
641 on the dynamics of the economy, and as such their in-use time may be shorter than that of residential
642 buildings.^{3,180} Non-residential building are thus a valuable part of the stock that ought to be
643 investigated more in the future.

644

645 Urban form, which reflects the physical layouts, structures, and patterns of a city, is also an important
646 driver behind the varying urban material stock levels. As cities are complex networks of interconnected
647 subsystems,¹⁸¹ characteristics of one subsystem are tied to the other subsystems. For example, the level
648 of infrastructure stock is intrinsically correlated to the density of buildings.^{171,182} In densely built areas,
649 the size of infrastructure stocks is about one-sixth of the total built environment stock, while this
650 number rises up to two-fifth in low building density area.¹⁸² Augiseau calculated the share of
651 infrastructure stock in Paris and its suburbs, and found that infrastructures account for 10% of the total
652 built environment material stock of the city, while it increases to 18% in the inner suburbs and 40% in
653 the outer suburbs, both typically less dense than the capital.¹⁷¹ Another important aspect of urban
654 fabrics is the vertical distribution of built environment stocks. Tanikawa calculated that in Wakayama
655 city center (Japan), material stocked underground in for example building foundations and sewer
656 network amounted for almost half of the total construction materials in 2004.⁴⁸

657

658 **7. Prospects and recommendations**

659 Built environment stocks play multiple critical roles in our socio-economic metabolism and a better
660 understanding of built environment stocks can assist in addressing many of our societal and policy
661 agendas such as urban sustainability, circular economy, climate change, and United Nations 2030
662 Sustainable Development Goals (e.g., SDG 11 “Sustainable Cities and Communities” and SDG 9
663 “Industry, Innovation and Infrastructures”). Based on the present review, we summarize below the

664 main roles of built environment stocks and infer their possible contributions to informing a sustainable
 665 socio-metabolic transition.

- 666 • First, built environment stocks represent an extensive reservoir of secondary raw materials,^{1,5-7,183}
 667 therefore a deepened knowledge of the amount, quality, location, and time availability of these
 668 material stocks can support urban mining, smart demolition, and waste management strategies for a
 669 variety of stakeholders (e.g., waste and recycling companies, architects, developers, and planners.
 670 This would lead to a decrease in the final amount of waste disposed, thus fostering circular
 671 economy and limiting the excess production of building material and lack of waste disposal
 672 capacity.¹²⁷
- 673 • Second, stock dynamics drive the material cycles and provide boundary conditions for related
 674 energy use and environmental impacts throughout the life cycle. The build-up, maintenance, and
 675 end-of-life management of built environment stocks lead to indirect energy use and emissions from
 676 their pre- and post-use phases (e.g., production and recycling of concrete).³⁶ The size, quality, and
 677 composition of stocks strongly influence the amount of direct energy used and greenhouse gases
 678 emitted for their operation to support human needs and activities (e.g., heating of a poorly insulated
 679 house).^{1,5,13,28,184} A sustainable socio-metabolic transition and understanding of future resource,
 680 energy, and emission pathways would require improved knowledge on the drivers (e.g., population
 681 size, levels of affluence, technological change, institutions, policies), patterns (e.g., speed of
 682 accumulation and potential saturation levels), and intra-linkages (e.g., systemic relationships
 683 between different built environment end-uses) and interlinkages (e.g., relationships between
 684 material stock density and energy use and emissions) of built environment stocks.^{185,186}
- 685 • Third, the built environment stocks entailed temporal and spatial lock-in effects are important for
 686 decision-making for the long term and at the urban scales. Stocks stay in use from years to over a
 687 century, potentially causing technological lock-ins and hindering a switch to more material- and
 688 energy-efficient systems. Decisions related to maintenance and development of built environment
 689 stocks are thus to be carefully considered before being implemented. Buildings and road
 690 infrastructure are also closely linked, and accessibility to services and commuting distances affect
 691 residents' preferred transportation mode¹ and thus influence transport-related environmental
 692 impacts. Understanding the interactions at stake between different types of built environment stocks
 693 would provide valuable information for urban planners and decision makers for building more
 694 energy-, resource- and cost-efficient cities.³⁶

695 • Last but not least, built environment stocks provide essential services on which societies rely to
696 satisfy primary needs (e.g., shelter, mobility, energy production and transmission, and water
697 distribution) and improve social and economic conditions (e.g., communication networks, waste
698 collection, and facilities for education, work, healthcare, or entertainment).^{1,6,36,41,185} Therefore
699 stock levels could indicate levels of human development. The historical patterns (e.g., potential
700 levels of saturation¹⁰¹) of built environment stocks in industrialized countries/cities could also help
701 benchmark future development of developing countries/cities. Such a stock perspective of human
702 well-being measurement has raised similar discussion in economics, where flow-based indicators
703 such as GDP have been criticized as they do not keep tracks of the assets actually producing the
704 GDP, such as infrastructures and natural and human capital.^{187,188}

705

706 Although attention to the importance of built environment stocks can be dated back to several decades
707 ago, the booming of empirical case studies on stocks started only after the 2000s. We summarize below
708 the main gaps and barriers in the development of built environment stock research, and put forward
709 recommendations to address them.

710 • Most studies were conducted on the country level, and only a few have a high spatial resolution
711 (often via an integration of GIS tool and bottom-up data) and a dynamic perspective. In order to
712 draw more robust conclusions on the patterns, drivers, and implications of built environment
713 stocks, more spatially refined case studies especially focusing on less studied geographical regions
714 (e.g., developing countries and cities) and stock categories (e.g., non-residential buildings and
715 infrastructure) are urgently needed. Meanwhile, consistent terminology, standardized methodology,
716 and larger-scale meta-analysis of existing data (e.g., based on a framework such as Figure 1 we
717 developed) would increase the comparability of results and facilitate identification of patterns and
718 drivers.

719 • Data quality and unavailability are identified as a major barrier for the expansion of built
720 environment stock studies, especially concerning the lack of information on buildings and
721 infrastructure lifetime and material intensity (when less representative and accurate averages were
722 often used). Material intensity databases^{189–191} and studies of transferability of data between cities
723 or countries,¹⁹² which allows for the analysis of regions where data are incomplete or missing, are
724 still sparse and should be investigated more. To this end, collaborating with key data providers
725 (e.g., municipalities, utility companies, demolition companies, and building contractors and

726 developers), harnessing new types of data (e.g., increasing amount of big data in social media and
 727 transportation), and nurturing interdisciplinary collaboration have been proven fruitful. For
 728 example, architects and civil engineers could contribute with knowledge on more accurate material
 729 intensity; GIS and remote sensing related tools and data in the fields of geography and urban
 730 planning would allow for a more spatially refined understanding of built environment stocks; the
 731 building energy use¹⁹³ and efficiency⁵⁶ modelling could help retrieve useful spatial and temporal
 732 data and understand the roles and drivers of built environment stocks.

- 733 • The role of built environment stocks in economic, social, and environmental development is less
 734 understood and thus often overlooked in governmental and industry policy arena. How such
 735 generated knowledge on stocks is useful for decision-making should be demonstrated via more
 736 dialogue among stakeholders in the future. For example, on an urban scale, the mapping and
 737 understanding of the dynamics of built environment stocks could provide an urban sustainability
 738 indicator (e.g., the weight of cities) from an important yet often overlooked stock perspective and
 739 help city councils in urban planning,⁴⁸ construction and demolition waste management,
 740 decarbonization, and dematerialization policy setting. Construction and waste management
 741 companies would benefit from detailed information on building stocks in implementing circular
 742 economy thinking within their activities, by reusing or recycling materials and products from their
 743 renovation and demolition activities. But if urban mining actions are to take place to recover
 744 stocked material, better understanding of the amount and location of materials (e.g., via GIS tools
 745 and architectural knowledge) and the technical feasibility and socioeconomic viability¹⁹⁴ (e.g.,
 746 coupled with Life Cycle Assessment, Cost Benefit Analysis, and other decision supporting tools)
 747 are yet to be analysed.¹⁸

748

749 In 1966, Kenneth E. Boulding wrote in his seminal essay “The Economics of the Coming Spaceship
 750 Earth” that, as the earth has no unlimited reservoir of anything, “what we are primarily concerned with
 751 is stock maintenance, and any technological change which results in the maintenance of a given total
 752 stock with a lessened throughput (that is, less production and consumption) is clearly a gain”.¹⁹⁵ Over
 753 five decades later, the statement holds even more true in an increasingly resource and environment
 754 constrained world. Based on the significance and gaps of stock research we identified in this review,
 755 we call for more studies and attention on built environment stocks, and particularly highlight the
 756 urgency and necessity for research towards standardized terminology and methodology to facilitate

757 consolidation of existing results and further larger-scale analysis, development of more spatially
758 refined case studies and material intensity databases, collaboration with key data providers and other
759 academic fields such as architectural engineering and geography, understanding of socioeconomic
760 drivers, and dialogue with stakeholders and decision-makers for harnessing knowledge on built
761 environment stocks in addressing societal sustainability challenges.

762

763 **Associated content**

764 * Supporting Information

765 S1: Materials and Methods, Complementary analysis of the body of literature, Reference list of the
766 body of literature. S2: Body of literature database (results of systematic screening of publications) The
767 Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: XXX

768

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772 Notes

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774

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785

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